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Characterization of Physical Properties, Bioactive Compounds and Pectin Extraction in Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) cv. Punjab Shweta as a Function of Harvest and Maturity Stage

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Abstract

The main objective of the study was to determine a practical follow-up for the pectin extraction from the whole guava fruit under optimum conditions and to explore the usage of pectin commercially. As guava fruits are available in two different seasons i.e. Rainy (monsoon) and winter respectively. While harvesting, the guavas were procured under different maturity indices viz. Immature green, mature green, over-ripe yellow and infested. So, Pectin was extracted with variation in season and four distinct maturity levels. Extracted pectin undergoes functional characterization and analysis for the best extraction yield. Pectin yield, Moisture content, Ash content and Degree of esterification of extracted pectin were analysed. Physico-chemical properties of guava fruits have proven to be better in the winter season and the highest pectin yield had been recovered from the mature green guava stage from winter guava crop.

Keywords: Guava; Pectin; Yield; Quality; Maturity; Season

Introduction

Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) is a climacteric fruit that is rich in vitamin C and belongs to the Myrtaceae family. Guava is a commercial fruit that is widely spread in tropical and subtropical areas (Kalsi et al., 2023a). Guava fruit attains fifth place in the total area and fourth in total fruit production in India. It is grown in almost all states, especially in Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra and West Bengal are the leading states in India for its higher guava production (Kalsi et al., 2023b). In the year 2019, the total area and the production of the guava fruit in India were nearly around 2.90 lakh hectares and 18.8 million tonnes respectively (Anonymous, 2019). As guava plants bear flowering which occurs during April-May and October-November as rainy (monsoon) and winter crops respectively. Harvesting is an important factor that affects fruit quality and should be done at right maturity level. Due to the various physiological and bio-chemical changes which arise during the storage and maturation of the desired fruit.

Guava bears fruits in the two distinct seasons of flowering viz. April–May and October–November in which fruits ripen during rainy and winter season, respectively (Mitra and Sanyal, 2004). Generally, rainy season guava fruit is poor in fruit quality as it is more affected by insects or pests as compared to the winter season crop. Whereas, the guavas of winter season are superior in quality, free from diseases and pests and make a premium price. Therefore, farmers often reduce monsoon crop by de-blossoming to get higher price. Fruitfly (*Bactrocera correcta* Bezzi.) is the main pest of rainy

season guava which causes spoilage whereas, the winter guavas are usually wrapped with polyethylene bags to protect the fruits from the fly infestation and able to fetch higher yield and attractive colour development (Mitra et al., 2008; Mondal et al., 2015).

Guava fruits are typically sourced from commercial fields immediately after harvest. They are categorized into four distinct maturity stages based on specific indices. The first stage, *Immature-green* (Stage I), is characterized by a dark green colour and a hard texture (Rashida et al., 1997). As the fruit develops, it reaches *Mature-green* (Stage II), where the skin transitions from dark to light green, representing its peak growth and market readiness. When the skin further changes to a light green or yellow hue, the fruit is classified as *Over-ripe* (Stage III), a stage highly susceptible to spoilage and often targeted by insects and pests. Finally, infested (Stage IV) guavas are those significantly damaged by pests (Roberto et al., 1990; Killadi et al., 2018). Guavas from these stages are either consumed fresh or processed into various products, including juice, jam, jelly, and puree (Kashyap et al., 2001).

During the maturation and growth of guavas, significant physiological and chemical transformations occur. One notable change is the increase in sugar content, which peaks at approximately 7–8%, alongside a rise in acid concentration. These changes result from the conversion of polysaccharides, such as pectin, into sugars as the fruit matures. Pectin, a complex polysaccharide, is located in the primary cell walls and middle lamella of higher plants. It predominantly comprises D-galacturonic acid along with other monosaccharides, including L-rhamnose, L-arabinose, D-galactose, and D-xylose. With its diverse applications in food technology, nutrition, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals, pectin is commercially sourced from agricultural by-products of plants. This study focuses on extracting pectin from the entire guava fruit while identifying the optimal maturity stage for both the yield and quality of pectin. Additionally, it examines the physical and chemical properties of guava at various maturity stages. The primary aim is to optimize pectin extraction and characterize it in laboratory conditions, contributing to the understanding of guava's potential as a pectin source.

Materials and methods

Procurement and preparation

Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) fruits were sourced from the local market in Ludhiana, Punjab. The fruits were washed thoroughly with warm water to remove any dirt, dust, or pesticide residues. After cleaning, the wet guavas were wiped using a clean muslin cloth and left to air dry for one hour. Subsequently, the physicochemical properties of guavas at various maturity stages were analyzed and recorded.

Physico-chemical analysis of different stage guava fruit

Several studies conducted at different locations have reported variations in sugar, pectin, and antioxidant levels in guava fruit at different stages of maturity and ripening (Singh and Jain, 2007). These factors are crucial for identifying the optimal harvesting stage to ensure high-quality fruits with prolonged shelf life. Such information was recorded for analysing the physical as well as chemical changes that occurred during the different maturity levels with variations in seasons i.e. rainy and winter.

True density

The true density of guava fruit was determined by using the toluene displacement method. A known weight of the guava sample was taken with an electronic weighing balance with its least count of 0.005g and the measured sample was immersed into a measuring cylinder which was partially filled with toluene liquid. The volume displaced by the fruit sample was noted down (Zalpouri et al., 2018). The true density was calculated by using the following relationship.

$$p \text{ (g/cc)} = W / (V_2 - V_1)$$

Where, W = weight of the sample (g)

V_2 = Volume of the cylinder after pouring the guava sample (cc³)

V_1 = Volume of the cylinder before pouring the guava sample (cc³)

Colour

The colour of the guava fruit samples was evaluated using a Colour Reader CR-10 (Konica Minolta Sensing Inc., Japan). To ensure accurate colour measurements, guava samples were placed in a petri dish in a way that prevented any light from passing through during the assessment. The 'L*', 'a*',

and 'b*' values were recorded (Kaur et al., 2014), where L* represents lightness, a* indicates the red/green value, and b* reflects the blue/yellow value. Chroma was then calculated using the following equations.

$$\text{Chroma} = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$$

Yellowness index

The yellowness index (YI) quantifies the degree of yellowness present in a sample (Rhim et al., 1999).

$$YI = \frac{142.86 b}{L}$$

Firmness

The firmness of the guava samples was measured using a Texture Analyzer (Stable Micro Systems, UK, Model: TA.TXT). A stainless-steel probe penetrated the guava surface by 2 mm to induce an irreversible change. The system was calibrated by moving the selected probe downward towards an empty platform and then upward to a preselected distance. Following calibration, the guava samples were placed on the platform, and the texture test was performed. The probe either compressed or punctured the guavas at different maturity stages. The maximum force required to break the guava samples was recorded and expressed in kgf.

TEST	Puncture test
PROBE	P/zN Needle
PRE-TEST SPEED	5mm/s
TEST-SPEED	1mm/s
POST-TEST	10mm/s
DISTANCE	10mm

Figure 1. True density & Firmness during different harvesting seasons and stages of maturity in guava fruits

Total soluble solids

The total soluble solids (TSS) content of the guava fruit was measured using a digital refractometer (Atago, PR-100, UK). Each sample was sliced and crushed with a mortar and pestle, and the juice was manually extracted from the crushed portions (>2 drops). The extracted juice was then placed on the refractometer, and the soluble solids content was expressed in °Brix. The reported values represent the average of three measurements per sample (Kaur et al., 2024).

Titrateable acidity

Titrateable acidity (TA) was measured following the method described by Ranganna (1994). Fresh guava slices were manually crushed using a mortar and pestle, and the extracted juice was filtered through a muslin cloth to obtain a clear sample. For the analysis, 2 ml of the filtered guava juice was titrated with 0.1 N sodium hydroxide solution, using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The titration endpoint was identified by the appearance of a faint pink colour, indicating neutralization. The volume of sodium hydroxide required to reach the endpoint was recorded, and the TA was calculated and expressed as grams/100 cm³ of juice.

Ascorbic content

Ascorbic acid content was determined using the AOAC (1984) method. A one-gram sample of guava was dissolved in 10 ml of a metaphosphoric acid-acetic acid solution, which was prepared by mixing 15 g of metaphosphoric acid and 40 ml of acetic acid in 450 ml of distilled water. From this, 10 ml of the extract was taken, and titration was carried out using a standard dye solution (2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol) until a pale pink colour appeared, which remained for 15–20 seconds as the endpoint. The ascorbic acid content was then calculated using the following formula.

$$\text{Ascorbic acid content (mg/100g)} = \frac{1 \times V_d \times V \times 100}{V_{std} \times V_e \times W_s}$$

where, V is total volume of metaphosphoric acid- acetic acid reagent (ml)

V_e = Volume of extract (ml)

V_d = Volume of dye used (ml)

V_{std} = Volume of standard (ml)

W_s = Weight of sample taken (g)

Anti-oxidant capacity

Antioxidant capacity was determined by evaluating the free radical-scavenging effect on the 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical (HiMedia Laboratories, India) following the method of De Ancos et al. (2002). The absorbance of the solution was measured at 515 nm against a blank using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Spectroscan 80DV, Biotech Engineering Management Company Limited, UK).

$$\text{Antioxidant capacity (\%)} = \frac{(\text{OD}_{\text{control}} - \text{OD}_{\text{sample}}) \times 100}{\text{OD}_{\text{control}}}$$

Where, $\text{OD}_{\text{control}}$ = optical density of control

$\text{OD}_{\text{sample}}$ = optical density of the sample

Flavonoids

One gram of the sample was homogenized with 10 ml of methanol, and 0.5 ml of the supernatant was diluted with 1.5 ml of methanol. To this mixture, 1 ml of 1% aluminium chloride and 1% potassium acetate was added, followed by the addition of 2.8 ml of distilled water to further dilute the solution. After standing for 30 minutes, the absorbance was measured at 415 nm against a blank using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The flavonoid content was calculated using a standard curve based on the relationship between blank concentration and optical density (Zalpouri et al., 2023). The standard curve used to measure quercetin concentration was prepared using a solution that ranged from 5 to 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Extraction and characterization of pectin

The washed guavas were cut into small pieces and the chopped pieces into the pulper to remove the seeds from the guava puree. Then, the guava puree is to be dried by using a refractive window dryer at 70°C until the puree is turned to dried flakes. Then, the dried flakes of guava puree were ground in a grinder. At last, the fine guava powder was obtained and packed in vacuum packets for further usage for pectin extraction. Pectin was extracted by the method given by (Pagen et al., 2001 and Devi et al., 2014). The different maturity levels of guava viz. Immature, Mature, Over-ripe & Infested were collected and turned into pulp. The different maturity guava's pulp was dried as mentioned above. Ten grams of guava powder was mixed thoroughly with 100 ml of distilled water having pH (1.5-2.5). The acidification of water was done by adding citric acid and pH was adjusted by pH meter. The mixture was then incubated at 60°C for a time interval of 30 minutes in an orbital shaking incubator (AS ONE Electromagnetic Orbital Shaker, Japan) at 150 rpm. As the solution was mixed well, it was filtered by using a muslin cloth to get rid of solid impurities present in the sample. 96% pure ethanol with an equal volume (1:1) was added to filtrate for the precipitation of pectin. After this, the samples were kept overnight for the complete precipitation of pectin. The next day, samples were centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 15 mins at a cold centrifuge (Remi Instruments, India) to separate pectin from the supernatant. As the maximum amount of pectin extracted would be considered.

Pectin yield (%)

Pectin yield was calculated as the amount of pectin extracted from the predefined amount of guava powder (Kumar 2018). It is expressed in percentage (%) & calculated as equation below

$$\text{Pectin yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of pectin extracted (g)}}{\text{Weight of dried guava powder (g)}} \times 100$$

Moisture content (%)

Five grams of extracted pectin was placed in a clean petri dish and weighed. The sample in the petri dish was then placed in a hot-air oven at 130°C for 2 hours. Afterward, the dish was removed and allowed to cool in a desiccator before being weighed (Ranganna, 1995).

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1 - W} \times 100$$

Where, W=Weight of petri-dish (g),
 W₁= Weight of petri-dish with sample (g),
 W₂= Weight of petri-dish with dried sample (g)

Ash content (%)

A 1.2 g sample of pectin was ignited gradually and then heated for 2–3 hours at 600°C. After heating, the crucible was allowed to cool to room temperature before being accurately weighed. The weight was recorded until it stabilized, and this final weight was noted.

$$\text{Ash content (\%)} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W} \times 100$$

Where, W= Weight of sample (g),
 W₁= Weight of dish (g),
 W₂= Weight of dish with ash (g)

Degree of esterification (%)

The degree of esterification was determined using the acid-base titration method. To 0.25 g of pectin, 1 ml of 65% propanol and 50 ml of distilled water were added, and the solution was placed on an electronic shaker to dissolve the pectin. The solution was then titrated with 0.1 N NaOH until reaching a pH of 7.5, with the volume of NaOH used recorded as 'a' ml. Following this, an additional 30 ml of NaOH was added, and the mixture was allowed to stand for 30 minutes. Afterward, 10 ml of H₂SO₄ was introduced, and the solution was stirred continuously. The mixture was then titrated again with 0.1 N NaOH, and the volume used was noted as 'b' ml. The degree of esterification was calculated using the following equation.

$$DE (\%) = 100 b (a - b)$$

Statistical analysis

The impact of physical and chemical parameters on the yield of extracted pectin was analysed using ANOVA with SAS software. The results of the analysis were utilized to assess significant differences among the various treatments at a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Physical properties, colour parameters and bioactive compounds of whole guava fruit

A detailed statistical evaluation was conducted to determine the effects of harvest season, maturity stage, and their interaction on the physical, colour, and biochemical properties of guava. The analysis revealed that true density was not significantly influenced by harvest season ($p = 0.1411$), but it was significantly affected by maturity stage ($p < 0.0001$) and the interaction between harvest season and maturity stage ($p = 0.0376$). On the other hand, firmness, L value, a value, and b value exhibited highly significant differences across all factors, with p-values < 0.0001 , except for the interaction of b value ($p = 0.0004$). Similarly, chroma and yellowness index were significantly impacted by harvest season, maturity stage, and their interaction, with respective p-values of < 0.0001 , < 0.0001 , 0.0013 , and 0.0005 . These findings underscore the independent and interactive influence of harvest season and maturity stage on guava's physical and colour properties.

Table 1. p-values for physical properties with variation in season and maturity levels

Properties	Source		
	Harvest season	Maturity stage	Harvest season × Maturity stage
True density	0.1411ns	<.0001*	0.0376*
Firmness	<.0001*	<.0001*	<.0001*
L*value	<.0001*	<.0001*	<.0001*
a*value	<.0001*	<.0001*	<.0001*
b*value	<.0001*	<.0001*	0.0004*
Chroma	<.0001*	<.0001*	<.0001*
Yellowness index	<.0001*	<.0001*	0.0005*

*Indicates significant terms at $p < 0.05$, ns indicates non-significant terms

The biochemical analysis further highlighted the significant role of the maturity stage. TSS were significantly influenced by maturity stage ($p < 0.0001$), though the harvest season ($p = 0.0804$) and

its interaction with maturity stage ($p = 0.0803$) showed no significant effects. Similarly, TA and TSS: TA ratio were significantly affected by the maturity stage ($p = 0.0018$ and $p = 0.0011$, respectively), while harvest season and its interaction with the maturity stage remained insignificant. Highly significant effects across all factors were observed for ascorbic acid content and antioxidant capacity ($p < 0.0001$). However, flavonoid content was unaffected by harvest season ($p = 0.8089$) but was significantly influenced by the maturity stage ($p < 0.0001$) and their interaction ($p = 0.0002$). During ripening, a consistent increase in TSS was noted across all maturity stages and seasons, attributed to the depolymerization of polysaccharides and conversion of starch to sugars. Acidity initially increased due to organic acid accumulation but declined at advanced maturity stages as acids converted to sugars, supporting observations by Batista-Silva et al. (2018). This led to an elevated TSS: TA ratio, aligning with Kundu et al. (1998). Firmness decreased as ripening progressed, with slight differences between immature fruits and other stages.

Figure 2. Change in colour during different harvesting seasons and stages of maturity in guava fruits

Antioxidant activity declined from the immature green stage to the overripe stage, corroborating findings by Benahmed et al. (2009) on flavonoid reductions in ripened fruits. This decline may result from the synthesis of complex phenolic compounds like tannins and lignin. Variations in total flavonoid content across maturity stages were attributed to environmental and genetic factors, including climate, soil, and species characteristics.

Table 2. p -values for bioactive compounds with variation in season and maturity level

Properties	Source		
	Harvest season	Maturity season	Harvest season × Maturity stage
TSS (°Brix)	0.0804ns	<.0001*	0.0803ns
TA (%)	0.7328ns	0.0018*	0.8878ns
TSS: TA	0.6817ns	0.0011*	0.7789ns
Ascorbic content (mg/100g)	<.0001*	<.0001*	<.0001*
Anti-oxidant capacity (%)	<.0001*	<.0001*	<.0001*
Flavonoids (mg/100g)	0.8089ns	<.0001*	0.0002*

*Indicates significant terms at $p < 0.05$, ns indicates non-significant terms

Table 3. Characterization of physical properties and colour parameters of guava at different maturity stages under distinct seasons

Maturity stages	True density	True density	Firmness	Firmness	L* value	L* value	a* value	a* value	b* value	b* value	Chroma	Chroma	Yellowness index	Yellowness index
	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter
Immature green	9.35±0.07 ^C	9.15±0.07 ^C	18.52±0.13 ^B	20.20±0.19 ^A	48.94±0.01 ^G	49.85±0.64 ^{FG}	-7.91±0.04 ^G	-7.80±0.03 ^G	8.25±0.03 ^E	8.55±0.01 ^E	11.43±0.05 ^E	11.57±0.01 ^F	24.08±0.08 ^F	24.50±0.27 ^F
Mature green	12.00±0.00 ^B	12.37±0.18 ^B	14.34±0.14 ^D	17.17±0.16 ^C	52.25±0.07 ^C	53.25±0.07 ^B	-6.85±0.07 ^F	-6.13±0.04 ^E	10.55±0.07 ^D	14.50±0.57 ^C	12.58±0.10 ^E	15.74±0.50 ^{CD}	28.85±0.15 ^D	38.90±1.57 ^C
Over-ripe	13.57±0.14 ^A	13.65±0.22 ^A	8.17±0.09 ^F	10.61±0.08 ^F	51.60±0.14 ^{DC}	54.75±0.07 ^A	-5.05±0.07 ^D	-4.15±0.07 ^C	14.25±0.07 ^C	16.15±0.07 ^B	15.12±0.09 ^D	16.67±0.09 ^{CB}	39.45±0.09 ^C	42.14±0.13 ^C
Infested	13.75±0.14 ^A	14.10±0.14 ^A	6.35±0.14 ^G	6.08±0.06 ^G	51.15±0.21 ^{DE}	50.3±0.07 ^{FE}	-2.88±0.04 ^B	-1.07±0.01 ^A	16.85±0.22 ^B	18.50±0.71 ^A	17.09±0.22 ^B	18.53±0.71 ^A	47.05±0.81 ^B	52.49±1.93 ^A

(A-G) Mean ± SD within a row with different superscripts are significantly different (p < 0.05)

Table 4. Characterization of bio-active compounds in guava with variation in maturity stage and seasons

Maturity stages	TSS (°Brix)		TA (%)		TSS: TA		Ascorbic content (mg/100g)		Anti-oxidant capacity (%)		Flavonoids (mg/100g)	
	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter
Immature green	9.35±0.07 ^C	9.15±0.07 ^C	0.19±0.00 ^{BA}	0.19±0.00 ^{BA}	49.88±1.32 ^{BC}	47.41±0.71 ^C	215.71±0.72 ^A	212.41±0.76 ^A	32.83±0.47 ^B	35.39±0.38 ^A	18.37±0.11 ^A	18.42±0.25 ^A
Mature green	12.00±0.00 ^B	12.37±0.18 ^B	0.18±0.00 ^B	0.18±0.00 ^{BA}	66.85±0.26 ^A	67.78±0.31 ^A	202.69±1.43 ^B	189.91±0.18 ^C	27.53±0.18 ^C	32.22±0.18 ^B	16.49±0.38 ^B	17.14±0.11 ^B
Over-ripe	13.57±0.14 ^A	13.65±0.22 ^A	0.24±0.01 ^A	0.24±0.01 ^{BA}	56.66±3.93 ^{BAC}	58.08±0.81 ^{BAC}	154.95±0.08 ^D	146.25±3.33 ^F	19.14±0.13 ^E	22.60±0.11 ^D	14.11±0.16 ^C	14.83±0.08 ^C
Infested	13.75±0.14 ^A	14.10±0.14 ^A	0.23±0.04 ^{BA}	0.22±0.01 ^{BA}	61.95±10.68 ^{BAC}	65.63±2.82 ^{BA}	136.59±3.53 ^F	104.92±0.42 ^G	8.02±0.20 ^G	14.81±0.11 ^F	11.75±0.18 ^D	10.23±0.16 ^E

(A-G) Mean ± SD within a row with different superscripts are significantly different (p < 0.05)

Figure 3. Change in bioactive compounds during different harvesting seasons and stages of maturity in guava fruits

Characterization of pectin

Pectin yield

The % yield of pectin extracted from the different maturity stage guavas by the above-described method varies from 1.83 % to 3.94 %. It has been shown that the mature green guavas show maximum pectin yield in both rainy and winter seasons by 3.41% and 3.94% respectively than other maturity level guavas (Fig 4). It has been observed that pectin content is higher in winter guava than the monsoon (rainy) fruits (Salunke and Kadam, 1995). The increase in pectin content during fruit development may be attributed to the conversion of other forms of pectin into a water-soluble form. Conversely, the decrease in pectin content at later stages of ripening could result from

enzymatic degradation as the fruit matures. Infested guavas exhibited the lowest pectin content, as pectin, a purified form of polysaccharide obtained through the aqueous extraction of certain edible plant materials, can be consumed by insects. So, the highest pectin yield (%) was in mature green guavas of the winter season than the other stage guavas (Table 5). So, the pectin extracted from mature green guavas was further utilized in the development of pectin-based formulations.

Figure 4. Change in properties of extracted pectin with different harvesting seasons and stages of maturity in guava fruits

Moisture content

Generally, pectin extracted should be less in moisture content so that can be stored for further usage. This also leads to improved quality as it minimizes microbial growth due to the production of the pectinase enzyme (Norazellina et al., 2012). As from the observations, moisture content was higher in infested guavas about 7% for both seasons but less in other stages of maturity. Mature green guavas showed very little moisture content in both seasons around 3.5% (Table 5). As variation in seasons, the winter season showed less moisture as compared to the monsoon season guava fruits.

Table 5. Characterization of extracted pectin

Maturity stages	Pectin yield (%)		Moisture content (%)		Ash content (%)		Degree of esterification	
	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter	Rainy	Winter
Immature Green	1.90±0.19 ^D	1.91±0.06 ^D	4.34±0.01 ^E	3.99±0.01 ^G	3.17±0.01 ^A	3.25±0.07 ^A	52.84±0.08 ^C	51.90±0.04 ^D
Mature Green	3.41±0.04 ^B	3.94±0.03 ^A	4.19±0.01 ^F	3.88±0.01 ^H	2.77±0.01 ^C	2.90±0.00 ^B	54.30±0.09 ^B	55.20±0.13 ^A
Over-ripe Yellow	3.01±0.11 ^C	3.47±0.01 ^B	6.28±0.03 ^C	6.12±0.03 ^D	2.71±0.00 ^C	2.70±0.00 ^C	47.36±0.04 ^E	47.49±0.08 ^E
Infested	1.83±0.01 ^D	1.84±0.06 ^D	7.88±0.02 ^A	7.57±0.02 ^B	2.57±0.01 ^D	2.67±0.01 ^{DC}	32.07±0.02 ^G	33.76±0.01 ^F

(A-H) Mean ± SD within a row with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

Ash content

The ash content plays a significant role in gel formation, making it a critical factor for pectin used in jelly and jam production. In this study, the ash content was lower than that of commercial pectin, which typically contains around 10%, indicating good-quality pectin. Furthermore, guavas harvested in the winter season exhibited higher ash content compared to those from the monsoon season, likely due to the higher moisture content during the rainy season. Immature green and mature green guavas had higher ash content (approximately 3–4%) compared to overripe and infested guavas, possibly due to their higher fibre content and lower juiciness (Table 6).

Degree of esterification

The degree of esterification of extracted pectin ranges from 35–55%. For immature green guavas, in both the rainy and winter seasons was found to be 52.84 and 51.90% respectively. Similarly, mature green guavas also resulted in 54.30 and 55.20% in the rainy and winter seasons respectively. From the above results, pectin extracted from the immature and mature green guavas can be categorized as high methoxyl pectin (HMP) because they show a degree of esterification more than

50% (Erika Kliemann et al., 2008). Moreover, pectin extracted from over-ripe and infested guavas resulted in low methoxyl pectin (LMP) as they showed the degree of esterification less than 50%. However, LMP could be used for gel formation with the addition of less sugar or without sugars. The rate of gel formation depends upon the degree of esterification which helps in setting gels quickly.

Table 6. p-values for bioactive compounds with variation in season and maturity level

Properties	Source		
	Harvest season	Maturity stage	Harvest season × Maturity stage
Pectin yield (%)	0.0003*	<.0001*	0.0037*
Moisture content (%)	<.0001*	<.0001*	0.0006*
Ash content (%)	0.0004*	<.0001*	0.0268*
Degree of esterification	<.0001*	<.0001*	<.0001*

*Indicates significant terms at $p < 0.05$, ns indicates non-significant terms

Conclusion

In the present study, pectin was extracted successfully from the different maturity stages of guava fruit and analysis of the extracted pectin. The whole study shows that winter season guava fruit has proven to be better for extraction purposes as the rainy season guavas are more prone to fruit flies. This study indicated that guava powder could be used as a natural source of pectin and could be utilised for the manufacturing of edible products in the nutraceutical, cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries. From the results, guava powder provides the optimum amount of pectin and can be used commercially.

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JK, PK, AKM, SB and RZ conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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